

How will the Greek innovation ecosystem evolve by 2035?

A full strategy process

Assignment submitted by

Odysseas Spyroglou

in partial fulfillment of the requirements of
International Future Strategist
Certification Programme

Assignment #3

Sep 2022

ICFS

INTERNATIONAL CERTIFIED FUTURE STRATEGIST

Contents

1	Executive Summary	3
2	Introduction	4
3	Elements of Trends and Uncertainties	5
4	Scenario Analysis	7
5	Assets: Strengths & Weaknesses.....	8
6	The Vision	9
7	The Strategy.....	10
8	The Action Plan – Strategy Proposals	11
9	Conclusion	12
10	References	13

COURSE	INTERNATIONAL CERTIFIED FUTURE STRATEGIST 2021
ASSIGNMENT	HOME ASSIGNMENT #3
SUBJECT	FULL STRATEGY PROCESS
GOAL	A full TAIDA-process for the focal question.
TASK	Building on the previous reports, run a full TAIDA process using taught methods. Describe the strategy generation and prioritization (single impact), just as their results and conclusions.
AUTHOR	Odysseas Spyroglou https://www.linkedin.com/in/ospyroglou/
EMAIL	ospyroglou@gmail.com
DATE	30 Sep 2022

1 Executive Summary

This report was submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements of the [International Future Strategist Certification Programme](#) by KAIROS. It is the third of three assignments and is building up on the previous 2 assignments.

The purpose of this final assignment is to do a full TAIDA process for our focal question: “**How will the Greek innovation ecosystem evolve by 2035?**”. What can we expect from it? What are the key factors, both trends and uncertainties that impact it, how are they interrelated and how important are they?

What did the previous 2 reports (assignments) cover and what this report will?

- HA#1: The **T (Tracking)** in TAIDA Model: the scanning of the contextual environment and of inner and near world, the identification of trends and uncertainties and a first analysis of them.
- HA#2: The **A (Analysis)** in TAIDA: picking up the analysis from A1 and evolving 4 most probable scenarios and starting the process of a vision building. The **I (Imaging)** in TAIDA.
- HA#3: This final 3rd report is picking up from the previous report and will focus on the final stages of TAIDA: **D (Deciding)** and **A (Acting)**

The **Deciding** stage of TAIDA is dealing with Strategy Development. It involves the creation of ideas and their forming into strategy suggestions that we can evaluate and decide on how to proceed. It's our way to **informed decision**. Finally, the **Acting (A)** stage will help us define our strategic goals and start planning the way to achieve them. The **report contains:**

- An **executive summary** with the most important issues covered including the selected strategies.
- The **elements of the trend and scenario analysis** that are needed to get the whole picture with at least five **drivers** (trends or uncertainties) and five **consequences** (described as threats and opportunities).
- A description of 5 **assets / strengths** and **weaknesses** and short description on how these were developed.
- **Description of the vision** (with some **vision points / corner stones**) and short description on the vision process.
- Description of the **strategy generation and prioritization** (single impact), their results and conclusions.
- A simple **action plan** in relation to the goal and strategy.

 Do you want to contribute?

If you would like to access the collaborative space used in this report and give feedback you can access it without the need for login here: <https://bit.ly/InnoGreece2> You can use the **comment** feature to provide any kind of feedback, thought or insight.

 Feedback & Comments in this report

You can check the previous reports [here](#) .

2 Introduction

Innovation is vital to the growth and prosperity of our society. It is the use of new ideas, products, or methods in areas that have not been used before. (Eurostat, 2012) Innovation is not restricted to technology or science. It permeates every sector and step of the production and distribution process.

The focal question of the study is **How will Greek innovation ecosystem evolve by 2035?** We examine not innovation in a specific industry or sector but rather, the process of innovation. How have Greece and EU promoted and will promote innovation and support new ideas that can lead to economic development and growth.

The **timeframe** expands beyond current framework programmes and initiatives (Horizon Europe), **Next Generation Europe**, **Greece 2.0** and will help be better prepared for the next generation of funding and initiatives.

The **primary purpose** of the study is to help the client, **International Development Ireland Ltd. (IDI)** identify opportunities in Greece and in the area, find new services in innovation support that will be needed by the private and public sector and even examine the possibility of establishing a new innovation hub or a regional office in the area.

The first part of the exercise (HA#1) identified the **trends and uncertainties** and ran a first analysis of driving forces and consequences. A cross impact analysis of these trends and uncertainties provided a map of their relationships and helped reach some very useful insights:

- EU is moving fast towards **Green and Digital transformation** making the related trends all too important. To this end, EU will invest significant funds.
- The **pandemic served as an accelerator** in Greece with new digital services introduced by the government almost monthly.
- Despite initial resistance EU approved for the first time a **common debt instrument (Next Generation EU Fund)** to support the **COVID19 recovery**.

Part 2 of the exercise (HA#2) focused on building the **scenarios for the future**. Four uncertainties were chosen to use as axis in our polarization diagram: **Economy, Geopolitics, Governance, Globalization**. The selected matrix was built on this cross: Stagflation and financial crisis to Strong Economic Growth / Protectionist, Populist, and introvert governance. Four scenarios were described: Star, Bubble, Endless crisis, and Endurance and presented with an early warning table.

In this document continue the TAIDA process evolving on the scenarios and their elements and maturing a vision which will generate a strategy and subsequently a tangible action plan.

EU's R&I programmes

In the next 7 years (2021-2027), EU has approved a budget where the support of R&I through various programmes is center staged. (2021-2027 Long-Term EU Budget & NextGenerationEU | European Commission, n.d.) Horizon Europe is the biggest EU research and Innovation (R&I) support initiative, but there are a lot more other programmes that also support innovation and a green and digital transition, like Digital Europe, Erasmus+, Interregional Innovation Investments, Innovation Fund, Single Market Programme and of course the Next Generation EU fund to support EU member states in their COVID19 recovery.(2021-2027 Long-Term EU Budget & NextGenerationEU | European Commission, n.d.)

International Development Ireland (IDI)

A provider of innovation support, capacity building and technical assistance to public and private organisations. [www.idi.ie]

3 Elements of Trends and Uncertainties

Throughout the research we identified consistent trends and uncertainties which were used to build the scenaria presented in the previous paper. We identified five (5) major trends and mapped their driving forces and their consequences:

- A **consistent drop of computing costs** in the long term, despite the recent disruption in the semiconductor market and the shortage of chips.
- An **acceleration of digitisation**, partly thanks to COVID19 and a new “low touch” economy that moves even more transactions online.
- A renewed **climate change awareness**, reinforced by a dreadful summer of fires and environmental destruction especially in the south.
- A **shortage of skills** especially for specific, advanced, and highly in demand skills and soft, horizontal skills necessary for all.
- A **sharing economy** that is expected to grow from \$15 billion in 2014 to \$335 billion in 2025. (*The Sharing Economy Is Still Growing, And Businesses Should Take Note*, n.d.)

TREND ANALYSIS OF DRIVING FORCES AND CONSEQUENCES			
DRIVING FORCES What makes the trend happen?	TREND	CONSEQUENCES What does the trend lead to?	HYPOTHESES Long term consequences?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Declining costs of computing - Expanding of connectivity - Declining costs in Telecom - Need for constant connectivity 	Affordable XaaS Lowering prices of online services and plethora of available tools.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More accessible computing for startups allows easier implementation of their ideas. - Close to zero costs for infrastructure. - New business models and services for both B2C, B2B 	Businesses and consumers move to a model where almost everything is offered as a Service (XaaS). Traditional ownership models decline.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need for further efficiency - Strive for cost reduction - Promise for a better/ faster/ cheaper service/ product. - Inevitable future (Digitise or perish) 	Digitisation Acceleration Transformation of Analog into digital for every aspect of business, life, government.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New or improved services/ products - Interaction between business < - > governments - Ability for deep analysis (Big Data, AI) - Preservation of Information & Knowledge - Easier Disaster Recovery - Income generation from new ideas, business 	Every business is a digital business. Digitisation facilitates integration of different business verticals through industries blending together and merging. Physical and Digital spaces are blurred. Major consequences in the future of work and life.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experience of extreme phenomena in everyday life - A new generation more environmentally responsible - Global Activism (Greta) - Compounding scientific proof 	Climate Change Awareness Global warming, extreme weather, biodiversity loss, scarcity of resources are acknowledged as major problems. Actions taken by governments & businesses.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Governments and International organisation taking initiatives and imposing new regulations - Businesses adopt environmentally responsible policies (ESG a requirement) - Citizens and consumers demand policies / actions. - Shift to renewable energy, decarbonisation, nuclear (?) 	Hopefully, immediate dangers are mitigated. Long term strategy by International Organisations (UN) leads to some valid results. However, danger is not easily averted. Some countries are more affected than others. Shift of agriculture production North since South too hot.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experience of extreme phenomena in everyday life - A new generation more environmentally responsible - Global Activism (Greta) - Compounding scientific proof 	Skills Shortages Lack of necessary technical and soft skills from workforce. Low interest of young generations to pursue these more demanding skills.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Less and less well trained people available for demanding and challenging works. - Lower quality workforce - Scarcity of specific skills, capabilities and experiences. - Ruthless competition for talent between corporations and smaller businesses 	Disruption of traditional education models. New corporate training and continuous learning are adopted. Companies provide initiatives for training into certain skills similar to military (guarantee payments, tax incentives, insurance etc.)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internet communities/ networks - Mobile economy (apps) - Decentralisation - Resource Efficiency 	Sharing Economy boom Wide adoption of new work models of sharing economy, peer-to-peer networks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New decentralised networks and collaboration opportunities - Increased efficiency of resource usage - Changes in the work models 	New models of ownership and work. You do not need to own (almost) anything when you can easily find it through a network.

In addition to the trends, we have also identified several more long-term **uncertainties** that we believe will impact our path to the future. These

uncertainties not only prevail but have grown in importance. With the pandemic still looming and new dangerous variants already in circulation, the situation is still unstable and unpredictable.

Even though there are no COVID19 restrictions anymore in Europe, the pandemic is very much still present with new variants appearing, cases spiking and China still facing disruptions due to the Zero COVID policy. In addition, a devastating war is raging in Ukraine with no end in sight, daily destruction and death and a looming global food crisis. Add to these the already high inflation caused by the disruption of the

UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS OF DRIVING FORCES AND CONSEQUENCES

DRIVING FORCES What makes the trend happen?	UNCERTAINTY	OUTCOMES	CONSEQUENCES What does each outcome lead to?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A new financial crisis - Unchecked inflation - Cost of climate change - Geopolitical Reasons 	Financial Environment Global, European and Greek economy.	A leap forward: Innovation Europe EU respond swiftly with a common strategy and make a leap forward by investing in innovation.	EU and Greece see the new crisis as an opportunity for further actions to support innovation & position as a global player.
		Surviving the next crisis EU steps up but not enough. Innovation is no longer a priority. EU still cannot agree on a common strategy.	Greece cannot realise its plans without enough EU support. The environment is not good for supporting new ideas and startups amidst a global crisis.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unresolved Issues - Authoritarian States - Injustice and poverty - New Civil wars - Refugee & Migration - Turkey's attitude 	Geopolitical Environment Situation in SE Europe and M.East.	A frail peace Status quo continuous with no major changes. EU takes a bigger role in the area. New alliances and active EU (France), USA role, deter aggressiveness.	Greece establishes a new diplomacy, based on soft power and strong alliances with major players. Defence sector embraces innovation.
		Sporadic microcrisis There is no major crisis but sporadic smaller conflicts and standoffs, inhibit growth and cost a lot.	Greece navigates and tries to insulate its economy and society from these crisis but the instability of the area holds back major investments from abroad (FDI).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unresolved Issues - Authoritarian States - Injustice and poverty - New Civil wars - Refugee & Migration - Turkey's attitude 	Role of Government How Greek administration responds to the challenges of the environment and what long term vision it creates.	A vision for the future Government adopts an ambitious vision for the future and manages to implement it successfully.	Greece establishes a new diplomacy, based on soft power and strong alliances with major players. Defence sector embraces innovation.
		A vision without actions Vision is there but cannot be realised or it becomes a half baked version mired with more problems than solutions.	Government succumbs to populism and does not go through with necessary structural changes. Populist parties disrupt the political space creating a new crisis.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - COVID19 persistence - Demands by employees - Social Insecurity - New work habits - Drive for Digital Nomads - Bussines Real Estate 	Workplace future Changes in the workplace, WFH.	A destination for Digital Nomads Greece becomes top destination for attracting talent and building new synergies between them and local ecosystem.	Digital Nomads become the bridge to link local innovation ecosystem with global players. A whole sector and ecosystem is build around this notion.
		Digital Nomads potential unutilized Digital Nomads come but no added value created. Only a useful tourism product.	Digital Nomads remain indifferent and uninterested in the Greek Innovation ecosystem. Innovation stakeholders cannot benefit from their presence.

supply chains, the energy crisis in Europe (and the world) and the already disappeared hopes and prospects for a swift post-COVID recover and it is more than certain that the financial and geopolitical instability will postpone the restart of the global economy for at least 3-5 years according to even modest analysts.

Although we still believe that the 5 identified trends will move upwards, meaning that we can expect **cheaper computing power, more digitisation, further environmental awareness, and more green investments**, a persistent inflation, and the disruption caused by the war in Ukraine may lead to a reprioritization of the EU policies. COVID19 may not be the wildcard we expected, but there is a new elephant in the room, and this is the major geopolitical crisis caused by Russia's completely unjustified invasion to Ukraine and Europe's dependency on Russian energy.

4 Scenario Analysis

Given the trends and uncertainties we singled out, we continued the scenario development exercise by the polarization of the most critical uncertainties. This analysis took place in Jan 2022 and unfortunately the economic and geopolitical developments since then vindicate it. We polarized 4 uncertainties: **Economy, Geopolitics, Governance, Globalisation**. We chose to use Economy and Governance as our 2 axes for 2 reasons:

- Major shifts in geopolitics and globalization are always reflected in the economy and this is our driving force here.
- Both economy and governance can provide some more actionable strategies. We cannot impact global geopolitics, but we can use governance to mitigate risks and create opportunities even in the bleakest of hours.

With this in mind, we worked with these 2 axes and with their extremes:

- From Stagflation and financial crisis to Strong Economic Growth.
- From Protectionist, Populist, and introvert governance (and government) to an Open, Pro-Market and pro-business Government.

Four (4) combinations were tested as seen in the diagram below. All of them provided challenging outcomes and fascinating scenarios. Of course, future developments are never linear. One single scenario almost never becomes the reality. It is usually a more complicated and intermingled process where we get variations and combinations of different outcomes.

5 Assets: Strengths & Weaknesses

Viable strategies are the intersection of the alternative futures we have envisaged (Should), the assets and competencies we can utilize (Can) and the specific vision we hope to realize (Want). So far, in the previous papers, we have worked with the scenarios (Should). Now it is time to consolidate everything and evaluate our assets in order to define our vision and develop our strategy. We need to contemplate the strengths and weaknesses for both the country in question (Greece) and for the client (IDI) since we will need to work with both to achieve our vision.

Greece has overcome a financial crisis that lasted more than 10 years. From a country in the verge of collapse in 2015, it has gone a long way, being today more resilient, more composed and fast improving in almost all financial, geopolitical and societal performance indicators. In 2021 Greece was among the 5 countries with an improvement of more than 25% in innovation performance in the period 2014-2021 (EU, 2020). We can identify 5 strong assets of the country that can hopefully guarantee its path towards success:

- **A pillar of stability** in the region: an active member all major institutions like EU and NATO, with strong links and alliances with USA, France, Israel, Egypt and the Gulf countries.
- **A maritime tradition** like no other: one of the world's largest merchant fleets (tonnage), more than 220 inhabited islands, Greek shipping companies among the best in the world, one LNG port and one more soon to be operational, Greece will be a transport and energy node.
- **A resilient society** with excellent human capital and a very strong and active diaspora, despite over 10 years of financial crisis the country survived and has recently exited EU's 'enhanced surveillance' framework after 12 years. Moreover, there is a weak but clear trend of Greeks returning and Europeans relocating to the country.
- **Excellent conditions to live.** A country with magnificent beauties, with spectacular mountains and more than 13.000 km of coastline, mild weather, wonderful cities to live and work.
- **Soft Power.** With a rich culture and a civilization of 28 centuries, Greece is repositioning itself in the global environment, reintroducing its brand after the many years of crisis. Despite COVIC19, the energy crisis and the unprecedented war in Ukraine, Greece's economy is projected to grow next year (albeit downward revised after the war).

Unfortunately, the country still has some significant challenges ahead: a large dept, the need for faster structural reforms and a political scene that is still mired by polarization, populism and slow justice.

A reminder:

The primary purpose of the study is to help the client, International Development Ireland Ltd. (IDI) identify opportunities in Greece and in the area, find new services in innovation support that will be needed by the private and public sector and even examine the possibility of establishing a new innovation hub or a regional office in the area.

IDI's Assets

IDI is in excellent position to operate in the country and transfer its knowhow and experience from the Ireland success story. Its work in the Balkans, Turkey and the Gulf has created a pool of experts with experience in SE Med area and links to prospective strategic partners in these countries. Links with R&I community of Europe will also facilitate better connections of the Greek R&I area and its European counterparts.

6 The Vision

After more than a decade of financial crisis, COVID19 and amid the recent geopolitical situation, with energy crisis looming and a war raging in the borders of Europe, we need now more than ever a vision that will help us achieve our potential. This is true for both Greece and IDI. During these years a lot of ideas have been promoted that resembled visions, but they were rather short-term targets than audacious goals. A real vision has to extend over a period of just a few years. It can span a few decades and be ambitious enough spark the imagination of the people.

Greece has been for many years in the last places of most rankings. Inherit problems, slow justice, lack of meritocracy, populism led from one crisis to another and to disasters. But the country was resilient enough to survive all these crises and to transform to something better after every disaster. This year, 2021, Greece has celebrated 200 years of its existence as a modern nation. Despite the doom and gloom in the geopolitical situation, the country has realised that it can actually be a power for stability, for innovation, for transformation, for environmental sustainability. Its goals are aligned with the goals of the EU and although Greece does not carry the weight of other European powers, it is still a modern, respected, democratic, innovative country. This is the big vision of the country: to remain in the core of the EU, to advance in every single aspect: in finance, in industry, in productivity, in health, in education. *To become a powerhouse of innovation and education and culture.*

GREECE: A powerhouse of innovation, education & culture

Greece becomes a paradigm of transformative innovation in energy, transport, maritime, tourism, agri-food thanks to the 3 pillars:

Education & Lifelong Learning

Redefining education at every level. Connecting learning with real life, skilling, re-skilling, up-skilling.

Continuous Innovation

Foster innovation, science, exploration. Bridge academic with business sector. Establish a successful quadruple helix.

Cultural Heritage

Draw inspiration from our ancient civilisation. Promote our classical studies, redefine citizen engagement, rebrand Greece.

The **cornerstones** upon which we will base this vision will be **education**, **continuous innovation**, and **cultural heritage**. We need society to embrace this new bold vision of the country, overcome the maladies of the past and engage in a common future. This **engagement** of the society and citizens can only be achieved through a new sense of belonging, a renewed national pride, a belief in our common European values and way of life. Greeks need to look once more in the past and keep the brightest ideas, so many of which are still relevant today, and commit to elevate Greece once more into a beacon of science and civilization. This vision although now abstract should define specific and measurable goals. Luckily there are plenty of KPIs we can choose from to substantiate our process and quantify our performance in the next years.

IDI will follow this vision and can become an integral part of it by supporting the country and its organisations in the pursuit of this grand vision.

IDI's Mission

IDI can play a driving role in this transforming environment. By providing technical assistance, capacity building, innovation support, help with Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), it can help both public and private organisations of the country, realize their potential.

7 The Strategy

The realization of such a grand vision cannot come without pains. A lot of things need to change. Structural reforms will be needed in education, in justice, in healthcare, in welfare, in governance. Provided that the future governments agree with this vision, the most important goal is to establish those constitutions that will be left along to perform their given mission, aligned with this vision. The lack of these constitutions that could operate with meritocracy, technical ability, commitment and outside of the political sphere is often the reason behind so many crises in the country.

The first step should be an **educational and academic reform**. Universities cannot perform their role because of disturbing minorities. Technical education has been almost abolished. Academic institutions are becoming almost irrelevant to modern challenges. By improving our **education** at all levels and by opening up our universities to the world (and private sector) we will spark new **innovation** and a new **culture** of learning. Our aim should be both to improve the performance of our students (e.g., under PISA's OECD rankings) and improve the position of our top universities by at least 100 places in the global university rankings.

At the same time, we can foster **innovation**, create a new culture of entrepreneurship and bridge the gap between basic and applied research and the market. Greece should attract talents from all over the world and give them the opportunity to work in a fostering environment. Greece can invest in the sectors and areas where it has a competitive advantage. The country has worked on its Smart Specialisation Strategies and has a solid long-term framework for each of the 13 regions (JRC EC, 2019).

Cultural Heritage is one of Greece's biggest assets. It is the country's civilization that allowed it to survive so many crises in the past and transform them into triumphs. Today it is underutilized and often distorted. Not only Greece can become a global center of classical studies for instance, but it could also bridge political and social sciences with technological progress: Ethics & AI, Social Innovation, politics and governance of technology.

At the same time the country can use these cultural values to **engage the citizens in the process**, build a new attitude of responsibility and ownership, where (hopefully) the role models will be scientists and entrepreneurs and innovators rather than TV personas.

No strategy will be successful if Greece does not address probably its biggest problem: Justice and its service. By reforming the **justice** system, speeding up the serving of justice, Greece can improve the rule of law and force better governance. Through better governance, clear legislation and commitment to the rule of law we can fight corruption, limit bureaucracy, speed up processes, ensure a leveled playing field.

IDI's Strategy

IDI has long experience and knowhow in supporting governmental agencies in similar transformations.

Bringing the experience from the Irish success story, an economy similar to the Greek one, the company will setup a Greek subsidiary and ground presence and create a team of both Greek and International experts that will be able to respond swiftly to the calls of the government and the innovation ecosystem.

8 The Action Plan – Strategy Proposals

The intrinsic limits of the current document do not allow a detailed layout of the strategy proposals that will serve the above strategy. Nevertheless, we have clustered our strategy proposals around our 3 cornerstones:

education, continuous innovation, and cultural heritage.

Education & Lifelong Learning

Nobody can deny the fact that education is the cornerstone of innovation and economy. Without well-educated citizens we will not be able to produce enough scientists and innovators. This process must start even at a kindergarten level and proceed to the higher levels of education, also providing the structures and tools for lifelong learning and continuous education.

Primary & School Education	Higher Education	Continuous & Lifelong Learning
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexible curricula • Training on soft skills • Focus on competencies • Educate better citizens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linking Universities w/ Industry • Allow private universities • Protect campuses • Raise status of GR Institutions • Attract researchers (brain gain) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentivize lifelong learning • Upskill, Reskill public servants • Provide Professional Certification framework

Continuous Innovation

Innovation needs a fertile environment. The changes in the academic sector will help, but further actions are necessary to ensure that we manage to transform ideas into solutions and products.

In the Public Sector	In the market / private sector	In Society
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use tools like Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP), Procurement of Innovative Solutions (PPI) • Incentivize process innovations • Establish R&I framework • Support Innovation (Subsidies, Grants, Loans) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support Tech Transfer • Incentivize Academia-Industry collaboration • Reskill researchers in solution commercialization • Communities of Angel Investors • Venture Capital investments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educate, communicate public in scientific method/processes • Promote new role models • Fight Disinformation, Misinformation • Engage citizens (citizen science)

Cultural Heritage

Ancient Greece is still considered a beacon of civilization in politics, literature, theater, mathematics, physics. The country can once again use its glorious past to build a prosperous future.

In Political Science	In Classical Studies & Humanities	In Nature, Environment, Energy
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Debate, discourse as a discipline in Schools • New curricula, studies in GR universities • Invite modern thinkers, philosophers to live, work in GR 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Courses on Greek foundations by top Universities in ENG • Create top courses on classical arts, philosophy, history • Open Museums, antiquities to global research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preserve Greek Nature • Create testbeds for experimentation w/ clean energy • Become a clean energy hub • Invest in wind, solar power

9 Conclusion

The world and the country are facing new challenges. Even before the end of the pandemic, Europe experiences a brutal war in Ukraine. An attack to our values and to our wellbeing. Inflation, energy crisis and even a looming food emergency are still in the day-to-day agenda of EU.

Greece has to rapidly adapt and respond to these crises in any way it can within the EU structure and making the best use of all available tools. Nevertheless, if the country and EU want to survive these crises as well, supporting innovation and building stronger more resilient systems of governance is the only viable course of action.

Both EU and Greece have now the tools to deal with these problems. Preserving societal cohesion and remaining true to our values, despite the hardships and the inevitable difficulties will pay off in the long term.

10 References

- 2021-2027 long-term EU budget & NextGenerationEU* | European Commission. (n.d.). Retrieved December 22, 2021, from https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/eu-budget/long-term-eu-budget/2021-2027_en
- EU. (2020). *European Innovation Scoreboard 2021 Innovation*. <https://doi.org/10.2873/340166>
- Eurostat. (2012). *Glossary: Innovation*. Statistics Explained.
- JRC EC. (2019). *Smart Specialisation Platform*. European Commission. <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/greece>
- The Sharing Economy Is Still Growing, And Businesses Should Take Note*. (n.d.). Retrieved December 23, 2021, from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbeslacouncil/2019/03/04/the-sharing-economy-is-still-growing-and-businesses-should-take-note/?sh=385eabd84c33>

Cover Photo by [Testalize.me](https://www.unsplash.com) on [Unsplash](https://www.unsplash.com)